

Attitudes of Faculty Members in The College of Education at Taibah University Towards Distance Education in Light of The CoronaVirus (Covid-19)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 20, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 01, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Distance Education, Faculty Members Attitudes, Corona Pandemic (Covid-19), Taibah University.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4967550</p>	<p><i>The study aimed to identify the trends of faculty members in the Faculty of Education at Taibah University towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19), and to achieve the objectives of the study, the descriptive analytical approach was used, and the questionnaire was used as a study tool. The College of Education at Taibah University, in the first semester of the academic year (1442 AH), totaling (152) faculty members. The results of the study showed that the attitudes of faculty members in the College of Education at Taibah University towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19) came in a moderate degree. The study also showed that there are no statistically significant differences at a significance level (0.05) between the averages of the study sample's trends towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19) due to the study variables (academic department, degree, gender). The study recommended the importance of adopting distance education as an effective strategic alternative to continue the educational process in the event of emergency or natural accidents, and to benefit from the best practices of Saudi universities in the field of distance education.</i></p>

Introduction

Distance education is one of the means of education using advanced technical media, and it is an innovative initiative with a strategic impact to improve the educational process, due to its flexibility in attending lectures, methods of education, evaluation and follow-up, low financial costs, and its connection with the needs of society and the labor market in light of a vision that keeps pace with the changes of the times. Accelerated provision of community services to meet the requirements of comprehensive development processes and future needs.

And in light of the crisis that the world is witnessing today, which may be one of the most dangerous crises in our modern time, which is the emerging corona virus (Covid-19), which began at the end of the year (2019), a crisis that caused the world to rapidly spread the virus, and had a negative impact on all activities and sectors. Life, most notably the education sector in general and university education in particular, so the government of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has taken various measures to limit the spread of the epidemic in order to protect its citizens. Among the most prominent of them is the suspension of work and study in universities.

The Ministry of Education announced that it is in accordance with the preventive and precautionary measures recommended by the competent health authorities in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, as part of its relentless efforts to control the emerging corona virus (Covid-19) and prevent its entry and spread, and out of concern to protect the health of male and female students and the educational staff. And administrative matters in public and university education and ensuring their safety; It has been decided to temporarily suspend studies in all regions and governorates of the Kingdom from Monday (7/14/1441 AH) until further notice (Saudi News Agency, 2020). The Minister of Education directed that virtual schools and remote education be activated during the study suspension period, as an alternative and quick solution to the continuation of the educational process and to achieve the least amount of educational loss to ensure the continuation of the educational process effectively while ensuring that the epidemic does not spread among the masses of students and the educational and administrative staff by providing direct lectures on the Internet. This provides the basic elements needed by the teacher and the learner and depends on the interactive learning method "Virtual Classroom Technology" (Florence & Michele, 2014: 193). It is an interactive learning and teaching environment that contains a set of activities that simulate the activities of the usual physical classroom that the teacher and students separate between them. Spatial barriers, but they work together at the same time, regardless of where they are (Al-Husseini, 2012: 17).

After the Kingdom's universities went through the experience of distance education in light of the Corona pandemic, this study came to identify the trends of faculty members about the experience of distance education, which was not optional in light of the spread of the Corona virus.

The study Problem

The observer of the conditions of education in different countries through the ages recognizes that education is affected and adapted to the environmental, political, societal, economic and health conditions ... etc. surrounding it.

In view of the current conditions and concern about the outbreak of Coronavirus (Covid-19) among community members and the suspension of work and study in universities, and to maintain the continuity of the educational process, universities tried to overcome the negative effects of this pandemic on education and get out with the least losses as possible and ensure students have good educational opportunities. , So it quickly turned to distance education, which surprised society and found itself obliged to go through a new experience without prior preparation to deal with it, which caused great turmoil in society, whether on the psychological, economic or social level, so the difference is big between the introduction of remote education forced by the repercussions of Virus Corona and the introduction of remote education convinced and in normal circumstances stem from the importance and necessity of this method in the educational learning process.

Given the importance of the faculty member's conviction and positive role that contributes to the success of the distance education experience in light of the Corona pandemic, and the need for concerted efforts and development of capabilities and skills to employ technology in education; This study came to reveal the attitudes of faculty members in the College of Education at Taibah University towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19), and its ability to achieve education goals and meet students' needs, and to create an interactive environment that replaces face-to-face learning.

Study questions

1-What are the attitudes of faculty members in the College of Education at Taibah University towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19)?

2- Are there statistically significant differences at a significant level (0.05) between the averages of the study sample's trends towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19) due to a variable (academic department, degree, gender)?

Objectives of the study:

1- Exposing the attitudes of faculty members in the College of Education at Taibah University towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19).

2- Disclosure of statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample's trends towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19) attributable to a variable (academic department, academic degree, gender).

The importance of studying

The study derives its importance from the vitality of its topic keeping pace with the current conditions around the world and the outbreak of the Coronavirus (Covid-19) and the suspension of work and study in various countries, which forced the education sectors to rapidly shift from traditional education to distance education and benefit from its technologies, and this necessitated that it keep pace with The universities of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia made this shift to prevent the spread of the virus among their students and employees.

The Coronavirus crisis was an opportunity to identify the direction of faculty members towards distance education. The positive attitudes of the individual determine the extent of his success in his work and his ability to overcome and overcome the obstacles and frustrations that he may face and impede his success at work, so that the faculty members have positive attitudes towards distance education that guarantees the success of the distance educational process and participation in its development, overcoming obstacles that face it and developing future plans To go to distance education as an alternative to face-to-face learning, especially in the event of similar phenomena, and the opposite means making more efforts to spread the culture of distance education, and to achieve a level of convictions of its importance in general and to limit the speed of the spread of Corona virus (Covid-19) in particular. And work to amend the direction towards it.

The limits of the study

This study was limited to revealing the trends of faculty members in the College of Education at Taibah University towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19) in the academic year (1442 AH).

Terminology of study:

Distance education: Shander defines distance education as: "that educational process in which the student is separated or far from the professor by a geographical distance that is usually blocked by using modern means of communication" (Al-Omari, 1423 AH: 70).

Flatah (2014: 83) defines distance education as: an educational style that relies on the use of information and communication technology to provide electronic lessons and lectures within the framework of a system directed

with the aim of providing a high-level educational service in efficiency and effectiveness and free from stereotypes and traditionalism in learning.

The procedural definition of distance education: an educational method related to the spatial and possibly temporal dimension between the professor and the educational institution and the student. It uses electronic media based on the Internet in presenting lectures and communication between faculty members and students through the electronic learning management system used in the College of Education at Taibah University to ensure physical distancing during Corona pandemic (Covid-19) period and developments.

Corona Pandemic (Covid-19):

The World Health Organization (2020) defines the Corona pandemic (Covid-19) as: the pandemic that resulted from the outbreak of the Coronavirus (Covid-19) worldwide, which causes illnesses that vary between colds and more severe diseases. Common symptoms of infection include respiratory symptoms, fever, cough and distress. And difficulty breathing, which affected all educational, economic, social and health sectors in most countries of the world.

Corona epidemic (Covid-19): It is a disease that affects the respiratory system, and it is contagious that can lead to death for patients who suffer from chronic diseases such as pressure, heart and diabetes. The disease is transmitted by coughing and sneezing and touching them to the mouth, nose and eyes, as well as by touching the hands to contaminated surfaces. By spray carrying the virus (SC, 2020: 4).

Theoretical framework

Not long ago, distance education was seen as a second-class educational method and was recognized as a supplement to traditional education, and then some universities began to teach general subjects using the remote education method to overcome the problem of increasing the number of students, as it was used in some courses of affiliation programs, and from Then the perception of distance education changed, and some Saudi universities adopted it in bachelor's programs in what is called "developed affiliation." Rather, the Saudi Electronic University was established, in which the study relies on distance education, and the university has proven its success among the rest of the Saudi universities.

The expansion of e-learning and distance education is due to their characteristics and to their positive effects. The study of (Edwards & Fritz 1997) revealed that e-learning is enjoyable and interesting and effectively achieves the desired educational results, and improves students' acquisition of concepts, as well as (Goodison 2001) study indicated that the application of e-learning and distance education has a positive effect on increasing the diversity and efficiency of teaching methods and methods. The study (Al-Dabbasi, 1423 AH) also proved that the distance education method is characterized by flexibility and is better than the traditional method in terms of level Academic achievement of female students and the desire for education, research, knowledge and enthusiasm in obtaining information increases. A study (Al-Saadat, 2005) indicated that distance education leads to the development of computer skills and obtaining information from the Internet.

The concept of distance education

Distance education is defined as: "An educational system in which educational instructions and instructions are exchanged between students and professors separated by time and space, in order to enable individuals to learn and overcome the circumstances of space and time" (Al-Dabbasi, 1423 778 :♣). It was also defined by Hilimberg (Hilimberg, 1997) as: "That type of education that includes different forms of study that are not under the direct and continuous supervision of teachers in lecture rooms and are separated by a spatial dimension" (Nashwan, 2004: 109). As for Al-Sharhan (2014: 47), he defined distance education as: "That type of education that is characterized by lack of direct and total communication between the teaching staff (teachers) and learners, as educational materials are provided through the local or global network (the Internet) Through the use of educational and communication technology.

Previous definitions agree that distance education focuses on:

- The spatial dimension between the teacher and the learner.
- That the educational process is done through the use of educational technology and modern means of communication.

Distance education goals:

- Achieving the principle of democracy in education and supporting equal educational opportunities (Arab Organization for Education, Culture and Science, 2006: 16).
- Reducing pressure on educational institutions so that everyone can find the opportunity to learn to overcome the deficit in educational capabilities (Abu Ghraib and Tawil: 1996: 622).
- Keeping pace with the development and continuous change in information technology and new technologies (Al-Mahdi, 2008: 702).
- The endeavor of educational institutions to provide appropriate education for the needs of a sector of learners and those wishing to enroll in university and higher studies appropriate to their abilities and capabilities and in the desired place and time (Al-Mousawi, 2014: 22).
- Spreading technical use and developing communication methods and skills among learners and community members (Al-Mousawi, 2014: 23).

- To benefit from the developments in the field of information and communication culture, in order to achieve the quality of education and improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the learner in what he learns (Arab Organization for Education, Culture and Science, 2006: 16).

Advantages of distance education:

Among the most prominent advantages of distance education mentioned by Al-Mousa and Al-Mubarak (2005: 53-54) are the following:

- Impact and effectiveness: Distance education is equal to or superior in impact and effectiveness than traditional education, but when it is used efficiently.
- Lack of cost in distance education: when compared to traditional education that has a high cost.
- The multiplicity of options in the methods of communicating the scientific material.
- The possibility of attracting highly qualified faculty.
- Distance education provides the teacher with several options in the methods of delivering the scientific material and the use of many methods of presentation and presentation in order to stimulate the learner and achieve the objectives of the educational process.
- Al-Jemni and others (2014: 98) also pointed out other advantages of distance education, including:
- Overcoming the distance obstacle as everyone can study from his location.
- Overcoming the hindrance of time because everyone can study at the time he wants.
- Ease of contact with professors, colleagues and libraries.
- Eliminating the teacher-dependent teaching process, so that the learner has a fundamental role in his self-learning process, so he becomes responsible for research and access to information and self-evaluation exercises to assess his comprehension.
- Improving the quality of educational content by using multimedia and digital technologies.
- Increase the absorptive capacity because distance education does not need much buildings, runways and departments.

In addition, e-learning will be the dominant educational pattern in the future, as the current generation is distinguished by its attachment to smart phones and the use of various applications, so the integration of technology in the educational process has become a global trend, and interaction with educational activities through mobile devices has become a catalyst for learning rather than sufficiency. Traditional study (Yulia, 2020: 49).

Negatives of distance education:

Al-Mousawi (2014: 23) believes that distance education has some drawbacks that can prevent obtaining the desired results from it, and the social and psychological factor is among the most prominent of those negatives as the interaction of students from computers and smart phones instead of directly communicating and interacting may lead to Isolation and loneliness, in addition to its reliance on technology to a large extent, many students may not have smart phones, computers, or a network (Hetsevich, 2017).

In addition, there is a fear that the learner will misuse technology, especially with regard to intellectual rights, through rampant plagiarism and fraud attempts, and there is also difficulty in controlling the submitted tests remotely (Amer and Al-Mousawi, 2010: 192).

This has cast a perversion on the quality and quality of distance education, and has made some educational decision-makers and planners - especially in Arab countries - refrain from adopting this type of education (Sethy, 2008: 36.)

In any case, there is an urgent need to set strict standards to overcome these negatives, in order to raise the confidence of decision-makers about adopting the method of distance education (Al-Mousawi, 2014: 24).

Factors for the success of distance education:

Al Musawi (Al Musawi, 2013: 12) points to the most prominent success factors in the application of distance education in the Arab world, including:

- Establishing an integrated strategy and a code to provide this type of education.
- Appropriate planning and design of curricula and courses in a thoughtful manner.
- Associating with institutions that have a long history in providing this type of education.
- Cooperation and partnership between Arab university education institutions that offer distance education.
- Use of technology on a good scale, and offer courses electronically or technologically supported.
- Adopting the synchronous and non-synchronous teaching method.
- Good preparation of teachers and employees in quality control mechanisms.
- Providing financial resources and budgets to achieve the goals of distance education.

Obstacles to distance education:

Distance education is one of the technologies that have increased in use over the past years around the world, and it is also considered one of the most growing fields in the field of university education, and the number of its users is expected to double every year. Despite this, it faces some obstacles and problems, the most prominent of which are (Al-Sharhan: 2014: 62-64), the following:

-Technical obstacles: These obstacles and difficulties stem from the speed of technological change in technologies, programs and devices, in addition to the difficulty of adapting to the new, which constitutes an obstacle to training to ensure the smooth flow of work.

-Educational obstacles: The biggest obstacles are in changing the educational thought in line with new mechanisms and technologies, which will present a new environment that requires new educational thinking, and continuous work to prepare faculty members and design curricula and teaching methods according to the latest scientific methods.

-Legislative obstacles: such as issuing laws, policies and regulations that provide: (protection of freedom of thought and the collection of knowledge, amendment of the promotion system and incentives to support the process of change, integration between different sectors, intellectual property rights, adoption of electronic administrations and electronic signature).

- Cultural and social obstacles: The success of distance education depends on several factors that must be met to ensure the achievement of its lofty goals, which focus on developing education and developing the tools necessary to make it more dynamic, so that it leads its mission in building pioneering generations and upgrading society to be a society of science, knowledge and production. This can only be achieved through national and national support for the project, in addition to effective programs for change, awareness and education.

Before the month of Rajab of the year (1441) corresponding to the month of March of the year (2020) it did not occur to any faculty member that distance education would be the only gateway to reach students and interact with them to achieve educational goals. Universities, the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia resorted to the sudden shift to distance education to maintain the continuity of the educational process and achieve the requirements of the second semester of the academic year (1441), and to achieve physical separation between students, faculty members and the rest of the university's employees in order to preserve their safety from infection with the Coronavirus -19).

The mosque Corona virus (Covid-19) is a new strain of Corona virus, with which humans have not previously been detected, and the World Health Organization discovered this emerging virus for the first time in (December 2019), after a group of viral pneumonia cases were reported in Wuhan. In the People's Republic of China, it is a viral disease that affects the respiratory system of humans at all ages, and the people most affected and susceptible to it are the elderly and those with chronic diseases, and it may spread among people by mixing with the infected, and droplets sprayed during coughing, sneezing and touching the tools of the infected person or the patient himself, Among its prominent symptoms are the following: fever, high temperature, cough, shortness of breath and general fatigue, vomiting and diarrhea, runny nose, in addition to sore throat, loss of sense of smell and taste. The Red Crescent (2020) has indicated that among the preventive measures and protection methods that help to reduce the risk of infection with this virus is the following:

- Avoid close contact with anyone who has symptoms of the common cold or flu, and avoid touching the eyes, nose or mouth.
- Clean hands with soap and water frequently, or use an alcohol-based hand sanitizer when leaving the house, or touch public facilities and others.
- Use the tissue when coughing and sneezing and dispose of it immediately after using it, or use the top of your sleeves or your bent arm in the absence of a tissue.
- Sterilization of all purchased items before they are brought into the home, and constant disinfection of surfaces in the home and office.

Taibah University, like other Saudi universities, committed itself to suspending studies in universities and schools and adopted distance education in order to complete the second semester of the academic year (1441 AH) and continued until the end of the academic year (1442 AH) with the aim of reducing the physical closeness that causes the rapid spread of the virus, as it followed Universities and all government departments, instructions of the Ministry of Health, such as: physical distancing, wearing a mask, continuous sterilization, and not allowing contacts or injured persons to enter workplaces.

Given the adoption of distance education as a result of the Corona pandemic, that is, due to an emergency and sudden, it is important to predict the degree to which faculty members accept it and how they deal with it and their behaviors towards it through the humanitarian aspects when using e-learning and distance education, the most important of which are the trends towards it and not limited to technical tools because achieving success It is associated with the presence of the positive trend and vice versa. Given the importance of trends in achieving success or not, this study came to identify the trends of faculty members in the Faculty of Education at Taibah University towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19).

Previous studies

The following is a review of previous Arab and foreign studies related to the subject of the current study, arranged in chronological order from the oldest to the most recent, as follows:

The study (Rabiai, 2017) aimed at identifying the attitudes of university education professors towards e-learning, and to achieve the goal of the study, the descriptive approach was used. The study sample consisted of

(205) members of university education professors at the University of Batna in Algeria, and the questionnaire was the study tool. The results of the study revealed positive trends for university education professors towards e-learning at the University of Batna, and the results of the study indicated that there were no statistically significant differences in the attitudes of university education professors towards e-learning due to the specialization variable, and the presence of statistically significant differences attributed to the gender variable in favor of male professors.

The study (Al- Dhaleai, 2017) aimed to identify the attitudes of students and faculty towards e-learning at Najran University, and to achieve the goal of the study, the descriptive approach was used. The study sample consisted of (673) students and (337) members of the faculty at Najran University. The questionnaire is the study tool. The results of the study revealed positive trends for faculty members towards increasing e-learning of scientific expertise, a desire to participate in the e-learning system, attend training programs and follow up developments associated with it, the need for faculty members to use it, neutral trends towards enjoyment when giving lectures electronically, and the need for learning. Electronic learning and their preference for e-learning over traditional learning, and that it is a waste of money, time and effort. Then came negative trends towards feeling tired during education using e-learning techniques, and that it weakens the interactive relationship between the student and the teacher, and his need for an effort that exceeds the energy of the student and the teacher, and his lack of credibility. The study also revealed that there are no statistically significant differences according to the variable of sex, college, and academic qualification. Based on the results, the study recommended the importance of developing an e-learning system to be able to face the difficulties and obstacles that students and faculty face while using this system, and the need to include the use of the e-learning system as a learning method in the descriptions of academic departments' decisions.

The study (Al-Shehri, 2019) aimed to know the attitudes of the faculty members in the Mathematics Department at King Khalid University towards the use of electronic education in teaching mathematics subjects to undergraduate students and students. The study used the descriptive approach in order to achieve its objectives, and the study sample consisted of (42) members. Of the faculty members (24 males and 18 females) in the Mathematics Department at King Khalid University, who were chosen by the stratified random method, and the questionnaire was the study tool. The results showed that there are differing trends among the study sample towards the use of e-learning in teaching mathematics, as (40.74%) of the scores for the arithmetic averages of the questionnaire items were medium and (59.26%) of the scores for the arithmetic averages for the items of the questionnaire were high, and the results also showed no significant differences. Statistical significance for the variables of sex and nationality, while it showed statistically significant differences for the variables in the number of teaching years and the academic degree in favor of those whose teaching years were (less than 5 years) and for the benefit of the lecturer. The study also recommended the necessity of training faculty members to use technical means effectively and develop their attitudes towards using it in the application of e-learning with all skill and professionalism, with the importance of designing a procedural guide that helps faculty members to use e-learning easily and easily.

The study (Abu Shkheidem and others: 2020) aimed to reveal the effectiveness of e-learning in light of the spread of the Coronavirus from the viewpoint of teachers at Kadoorie University in Palestine, and to achieve the objectives of the study, the descriptive analytical approach was adopted, and the study sample consisted of (50) faculty members in Kadoorie University who taught during the period of the spread of Coronavirus through the e-learning system, and the necessary data were collected using the questionnaire. The results of the study revealed that the study sample's evaluation of the effectiveness of e-learning in light of the spread of the Coronavirus, from their viewpoint, was moderate. The researchers recommended holding training courses in the field of e-learning for both teachers and students, and helping to get rid of all obstacles that prevent benefiting from the e-learning system followed and the need to combine face-to-face education with e-learning in higher education institutions in the future.

The study (Al-Zahrani, 2020) aimed to identify the trends of faculty members at Umm Al-Qura University towards employing e-learning tools, "the blackboard platform" in the educational process, in line with the repercussions of quarantine due to the Corona virus, and to achieve the objectives of the study, reliance was on the descriptive approach, and a sample was formed. The study consisted of (90) faculty members at Umm Al-Qura University, who were chosen randomly, and the questionnaire was the study tool. The results indicated that there are positive and high trends among faculty members at Umm Al-Qura University towards employing the "blackboard platform" in the educational process, and the study sample showed their desire to use the "blackboard platform" as a strategic option and not just an alternative in the educational process. There are no differences in the trends towards employing the "blackboard platform" in the educational process among faculty members due to the study variables (gender, specialization, and academic degree).

In addition, the study (Shaghouf and ALWaldah, 2020) aimed to identify the trends of faculty members towards electronic education in Libya in emergency and crisis situations, and to achieve the objectives of the study, the descriptive curriculum was adopted, and the study sample consisted of (190) faculty members in Libyan universities. The study is the questionnaire. The study found that the general trend of faculty members in Libyan

universities towards employing e-learning was (high), and the results showed that there were no differences in the attitudes of faculty members for the following variables: (gender, academic qualification, academic degree, years of experience, teaching field).

The study (Al-Mabrouk and Al-Zafri, 2021) dealt with identifying the attitudes of faculty members at the Islamic University of Al-Asaied Muhammad bin Ali Al-Sanussi in Al-Bayda in Libya towards the Internet and its use in university education in distance learning in light of the Corona pandemic. The sample of the study consisted of (100) faculty members who were chosen randomly, and the necessary data were collected using the teachers' attitude scale (Muhaisen, 2009). The results of the study revealed the faculty members' attitudes towards the Internet and their use in university education in distance learning were positive and that the most prevailing trend among faculty members is the use of the Internet in order to obtain knowledge, and it is also evident that the faculty members are spread among them the trend of using the Internet in the interaction between colleagues and students.

Comments on previous studies

The current study aimed to identify the trends of faculty members towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic, and most previous studies agreed with it in the main objective with the exception of the study (Abu Shkheidem and others: 2020) that aimed to reveal the effectiveness of e-learning in light of the spread of the Corona virus from the point of view. The teachers looked, and linked (Abu Shkheidem and others: 2020); (Al-Zahrani, 2020), (Al-Mabrouk and Al-Zafri, 2021) their study of the Corona pandemic, and in terms of approach, all previous studies used the descriptive approach, and the current study and my studies (Abu Shkheidem and others: 2020) used; (Al-Mabrouk and Al-Zafri, 2021) The Correlational Descriptive Approach, and in terms of the study tool, the current study and all previous studies used the questionnaire as a tool to collect data, and in terms of society and the sample, the current study community and all previous studies are members of the faculty and the uniqueness of the study community (Al- Dhaleai, 2017) by integrating a survey Opinions of students and faculty members.

It is noticed from the previous presentation that all previous studies were concerned with the attitudes of faculty members towards e-learning and distance education and the "blackboard platform" as one of their tools, and that the environment for applying studies was varied from several countries (Algeria, Palestine, Libya, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in their different regions) And that all studies are recent, and this indicates the importance of the topic and that it is of interest to many countries, and thus it was important to pay attention to such topics in question.

Study procedures

Study Approach

The study relied on the descriptive and analytical approach to answer the study's questions and achieve its objectives. It is one of the forms of structured scientific analysis and interpretation to describe a specific phenomenon or problem and quantify it quantitatively, by collecting codified data and information about the phenomenon or problem, classifying it, analyzing it and subjecting it to accurate studies (Melhem, 2000: 324)

The study population consisted of all faculty members in the College of Education at Taibah University in the first semester of the academic year (1442 AH), whose number is (152) teaching staff (Ministry of Education: 1441 AH), and the following table shows the distribution of the study population.

Table (1) Distribution of the study population according to the variables (academic department, academic degree, gender)

Academic department	gender	professor	Co-professor	Assistant Professor	total
education basics	male	5	3	4	12
	female	1	1	6	8
educational administration	male	2	5	6	13
	female	1	1	3	5
Physical Education and Sports Sciences	male	4	7	5	16
	female	1	0	0	1
Special Education	male	3	3	4	10
	female	0	1	2	3

Art education	male	1	3	2	6
	female	0	0	5	5
Curriculum and Instruction	male	5	10	13	28
	female	1	4	14	19
Education technologies	male	1	1	2	4
	female	0	2	5	7
Educational Psychology	male	2	5	1	8
	female	0	0	7	7
Total		27	46	79	152

Source: Ministry of Education, Ministry of Planning and Development Agency, Education Statistics and Decision Support Center (DhulQa'dah, 1441 A.H.)

The researcher distributed the study tool to the study population of (152) faculty members, and the return of the tools was (97) tools, which represented (64%) of the study population.

Study tool

To gain access to the data and information necessary to achieve the goals of the study, the researcher prepared a closed questionnaire to measure the attitudes of faculty members in the Faculty of Education at Taibah University towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19), using the help of relevant studies and educational literature.

Validate the study tool:

The validity of the study instrument was measured by:

- Content validity or apparent validity: The study tool was presented to (14) scientific arbitrators from the faculty members in Saudi universities, and the researcher studied their observations and amendments were made in light of the recommendations and opinions of the arbitration panel.
- Validity of internal consistency: To verify the validity of the internal consistency of the tool, the Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated to measure the relationship between each statement and the overall degree of the questionnaire, and the results were as follows:

Table (2) the internal consistency of the study tool

A	R	A	R	A	R
A1	**00.355	A8	**00.750	A15	**00.626
A2	**00.459	A9	**00.655	A16	**00.305
A3	**00.528	A10	**00.637	A17	**00.564
A4	**00.482	A11	**00.422	A18	**00.686
A5	**00.537	A12	**00.476	A19	**00.608
A6	**00.334	A13	**00.530	A20	**00.708
A7	**00.544	A14	**00.476		

** is function at 0.05

It is evident from Table (2) that all the statement is statistically significant at a level of significance (0.05), and this indicates that the study tool is truthful and measures the characteristic or phenomenon that was designed to measure it.

Stability of the study tool

The researcher verified the stability of the study tool by using the two methods of the reliability coefficient, Cronbach's alpha and split-half reliability, and the following table shows that:

Table (3) stability coefficients for the study tool

The number of phrases	Cronbach's alpha test	split-half reliability test
20	0.864	0.778

It is evident from Table (3) that the stability coefficients for the study tool are high, and this indicates the consistency of the data and that the study tool gives the same results if it is re-applied to the same individuals or phenomena and under similar conditions to the greatest possible extent.

Determine the criterion or criterion for judging the results of the study

The data were interpreted according to Likert's five-point scale in each dimension of the study, where the degree of (approval) was formed from the following five-point gradient (very large, large, medium, weak, and not completely agreeing) and the weight was determined as in the following table:

Table (4) the degrees and limits of the study results criteria categories according to the five Likert scale the weight

the weight	The criterion for judging results	Weighted average
5	Agree with very much degree	From 4.2 - 5
4	Agree with high degree	From 3.4 – 4.19
3	Agree with medium degree	From 2.6 – 3.39
2	Agree with weakly degree	From 1.8 – 2.59
1	Totally disagree	Form 1 – 1.79

Statistical processors

To achieve the objectives of the study, the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) program was used to analyze the data and extract the results and interpret them, as follows:

- Duplicates to describe the characteristics of the study population.
- The arithmetic means, standard deviations, and the arrangement of the responses of the study population to the statements according to the values of the arithmetic mean.
- Pearson correlation coefficient to verify the internal consistency of the terms of the study tool.
- Cronbach's alpha coefficient and half-segmentation to verify the stability of the study instrument.
- One way ANOVA test or called F-test to find out the significance of the differences between the arithmetic averages between more than two independent groups, with respect to the two variables (academic department, academic degree).
- T-test to determine the statistically significant differences between two independent groups, with regard to the (gender) variable.

Results:

The following is a presentation of the results of the study questions, which came as follows:

Results related to the first question: What are the attitudes of faculty members in the College of Education at Taibah University towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19)?

In order to answer this question, arithmetic averages, standard deviations and the arrangement of the attitudes of faculty members in the Faculty of Education at Taibah University towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19) were found, and the results were as follows:

Table (5) Attitudes of faculty members in the College of Education at Taibah University towards distance education In light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19)

m	Descending Order of Expressions according to averages	Arithmetic mean	standard deviation	Degree of agreement	arrangement
1	Distance education is an effective strategy to continue the educational process in the event of emergency or natural accidents.	4.6804	0.49046	Very large	1
16	Distance education makes me feel any service to my community and my country to protect against the Coronavirus.	4.5464	0.72199	Very large	2
8	Have sufficient skills to use the distance learning system followed at the university.	4.1856	1.02398	large	3
17	Distance education has become an urgent necessity.	4.0412	0.90043	large	4
2	The distance learning method has overcome resistance to its use in the educational process.	4.0309	0.74237	large	5
3	The strengths and weaknesses of the university's remote education system became clear.	3.9175	0.77285	large	6
4	The university library has digitized many of its holdings and made them available to researchers free of charge.	3.8454	0.63476	large	7
7	I feel I am able to manage the electronic class.	3.6186	0.96224	large	8
9	Distance education technologies help in diversifying the ways of presenting	3.5155	1.01153	large	9

	scientific material.				
5	I benefited from the remote professional development programs offered by the university.	3.3918	1.10450	medium	10
15	I feel satisfied with the distance education system followed in the university.	3.3196	0.68536	medium	11
10	Distance education facilitates communication between teacher and students	3.2577	0.78100	medium	12
20	Distance education is fun and effective.	3.2577	0.97124	medium	13
18	I support the merging of traditional and distance education in the future.	3.1237	0.69609	medium	14
13	Ease of setting up remote electronic tests.	2.5361	0.79138	weak	15
12	Ease of converting the paper scientific material into a digital one.	2.4948	0.61447	weak	16
14	Ease of measuring the learning outcomes of remote learners.	2.4124	0.85089	Weak	17
6	Distance education saves time and effort.	2.3196	0.99526	Weak	18
11	Students have sufficient skills to use the distance education system.	2.0309	0.88334	weak	19
19	The transition to distance education has been made with flexibility	1.6907	0.69763	Completely disagree	20
Attitudes of faculty members in the College of Education at Taibah University towards distance education in light of the Coronavirus (Covid-19)		3.3108	0.43894	medium	

It is evident from Table (5) that the general arithmetic mean value of the attitudes of faculty members in the College of Education at Taibah University towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19) is equal to (3.310), and the value of the standard deviation is equal to (0.438), and this value is located in The third category of the scale, which indicates a degree (medium), and this result can be explained by the fact that most of the courses at Taibah University are taught in attendance, and during the Corona pandemic the shift to distance education was surprising without any alternative option. Teaching has actual practice and sufficient experience in this field.

This result is consistent with the result of the study (Abu Shkheidem and others: 2020), which indicated that the effectiveness of e-learning in light of the spread of the Corona virus from the viewpoint of teachers at Kadoorie University was moderate. This result also differs with the result of the study (Rabei, 2017), which concluded that the attitudes of university education professors towards e-learning at the University of Batna were positive, and the study (Al-Zahrani, 2020) whose results indicated the presence of positive and high trends among faculty members at Umm Al-Qura University. Towards employing the "blackboard platform" in the educational process, and the study (Shaghouf and ALWaldah, 2020), which concluded that the general trend of faculty members in Libyan universities towards employing e-learning was (high), and the study of (Al-Mabrouk and Al-Zafri, 2021), whose results revealed trends Positive for faculty members towards the Internet and its use in university education in distance learning.

As shown in Table (5), the arithmetic averages vary in the attitudes of faculty members in the College of Education at Taibah University towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19).

- The first group: has a mean (from 4.20 to 5) and degree of approval (very large):

Phrase (1) "Distance education is an effective strategy to continue the educational process in the event of emergency or natural accidents," and the phrase (16) "Distance education makes me feel that I am providing a service to my community and my country to protect against Coronavirus." This result may be attributed to the high awareness of the members of the study community about the importance of distance education and its important role in the continuity of the educational process during the period of the Corona pandemic, while ensuring social distancing to protect students and faculty members from infection with the virus.

This result is consistent with the result of the study (Al-Shehri, 2019), which indicated that the trends of faculty members in the Mathematics Department at King Khalid University towards the use of e-learning in teaching mathematics subjects to undergraduate students were mostly high by (59.26%) of the scores of the arithmetic averages of the items The questionnaire.

- The second group: its arithmetic mean between (from 3.40 to 4.19) and the degree of approval (large):

Phrase (8): "I have sufficient skills to use the distance education system followed at the university." This result can be explained by the fact that the study community had the basic skills when they used the distance learning system at the beginning of the Corona pandemic, and the phrase (17): "Distance education has become An urgent necessity "especially when emergency or natural accidents happen, and the phrase (2):" The distance education method has overcome resistance to its use in the educational process "after its mandatory experience during the Corona pandemic increased confidence in him and the faculty member possessing the basic skills necessary to deal with him, and the phrase 3): "The strengths and weaknesses of the distance education system followed at the university were evident." Through practice, the available capabilities were discovered, which are preferred to be added and developed, and the phrase (4): "The university library digitized many of its holdings and made them available to researchers free of charge" as a main service and an important step that should be Tracking with digital development, the phrase (7): "I feel that I am able to manage the electronic classroom", and the phrase (9): "Distance education technologies help in the diversity of methods of presenting scientific material." Among the advantages of educational technologies are the considerations of individual differences through multiple ways Z scientific material in an interesting and easy way.

This result is consistent with the result of the study (Al-Dhali, 2017), which revealed positive trends for faculty members at Najran University towards increasing e-learning for practical experiences, and the faculty members having to use it, and the study (Al-Mabrouk and Al-Zafri, 2021), the results of which revealed that the most prevailing trends of The faculty is using the internet in order to obtain knowledge. This result also differs with the result of the study (Al-Dhali, 2017), which revealed neutral trends of faculty members at Najran University towards the need for e-learning, and negative trends towards feeling tired during education using e-learning techniques.

- The third group: its arithmetic mean between (2.60 to 3.39) and the degree of approval (medium):

Phrase (5): "I benefited from the professional development programs offered by the remote university." This result is attributed to Taibah University's keenness to improve the educational process and facilitate all means to develop the skills of faculty members in all fields, especially distance education, as this stage requires of actual need. However, due to lack of time, perhaps the preparation for the professional development programs offered by the university was not at the level of ambition, and the statement (15): "I feel satisfied with the distance education system followed at the university," and the phrase (10): "Distance education facilitates communication between the teacher And students, "This result came to a moderate degree because of the difference in the timing of the student and the teacher entering the means of communication and responding to them, either due to family or health conditions, or the participation of more than one person in the home of the computer or smart devices, and the phrase (20):" Distance education is fun and effective. " , And the phrase (18): "I support the merging between traditional and distance education in the future." Because the faculty members touched the pleasure and benefit of both the teacher and the learner alike, they supported the merging between traditional and distance education in the future.

This result is consistent with the result of the study (Al-Dhali, 2017), which revealed neutral tendencies of faculty members at Najran University towards enjoyment when giving lectures electronically, and the result of the study (Al-Shehri, 2019), which indicated that the trends of faculty members in the Department of Mathematics at King University Khaled towards the use of e-learning in teaching mathematics subjects to undergraduate students was average (40.74%) of the arithmetic mean scores for the paragraphs of the questionnaire. This result also differs with the result of the study (Al-Dhali, 2017), which revealed positive trends for faculty members at Najran University towards the desire to participate in the e-learning system, attend training programs and follow up on developments related to it, as well as negative trends about the weakness of the interactive relationship between the student and the teacher. In distance education, and the study (Al-Zahrani, 2020), the results of which indicated a high desire among faculty members at Umm Al-Qura University to use the "blackboard platform" as a strategic choice and not just an alternative in the educational process, and the study of (Al-Mabrouk and Al-Zafri, 2021) whose results revealed That the faculty members spread among them the trend of using the Internet in interaction between colleagues and students.

- The fourth group: its arithmetic mean between (from 1.80 to 2.59) and the degree of approval (weak):

Phrase (13): "Ease of developing electronic remote exams," and the phrase (14): "Ease of measuring the learning outcomes of distance learners." Despite the average attitudes of faculty members at Taibah University towards their feeling of the enjoyment and effectiveness of distance education and their support for the merging of education However, it is not easy to develop electronic tests that measure learning outcomes for distance learners, and the reason for this may be due to the lack of training in developing such kind of tests, the need for great experience in this field, as well as the expectation of students cheating and the circulation of answers regarding Between them through various means of communication, which may weaken the credibility of students' results, and the phrase (12): "Ease of converting the paper-based scientific material into digital

material,” and the phrase (6): “Distance education saves time and effort.” Although distance education techniques help With regard to the diversity of methods of presenting the scientific material, however, it is difficult for some teachers to convert the paper scientific material into a digital one, and therefore they spend a lot of time and effort in extracting the scientific material in an attractive way with attention to taking into account the individual differences between students, and the phrase (11): “Students have sufficient skills to use the distance education system.” This may be due to poor prior training of students on the distance education system, or because of the large number of distractions around distance learners.

This result is consistent with the result of the study (Al-Dhali, 2017), which revealed negative trends of faculty members at Najran University towards the need for distance education to an effort that exceeds the capacity of the student and the teacher, and his lack of credibility. This result also differs with the result of the study (Al-Dhali, 2017), which revealed neutral trends of faculty members at Najran University towards their preference for e-learning over distance education, and that it wastes money, time and effort.

- The fifth group: average between (1 to 1.79) and the degree of approval (not completely agree):

Phrase (19): “The transition to distance education was done with flexibility,” because the decision to suspend studies and switch to remote education was sudden and without prior preparation due to the repercussions of the Corona pandemic.

Results related to the second question: Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance (0.05) between the averages of the study population’s attitudes towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19) attributable to a variable (academic department, degree, gender)?

In order to answer this question and reveal the statistical significance of the differences between the averages of the responses of the members of the study community towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19), the One Way ANOVA was used for the two variables (academic department, academic degree). Using the T-Test for the (gender) variable. The results were as follows:

- Academic section variable:

Table (6) the results of the One Way ANOVA analysis of the differences between the averages of the study community’s responses towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19) according to a variable (academic section)

The source of the contrast	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Average squareness	F value	indication
Between groups	1.051	7	0.150	0.766	0.617
Within groups	17.445	89	0.196		No indication
Total	18.496	96			

*function at 0.05

It is evident from Table (6) that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance (0.05) between the averages of the study sample’s trends towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19) due to the academic department variable, where the value of P was (0.766), It is not a function at (0.617).

This result is consistent with the result of the study (Rabei, 2017), whose results indicated that there are no statistically significant differences in the attitudes of university education professors at the University of Batna towards e-learning due to the variable (specialization), and the result of the study (Zahrani, 2020), whose results indicated that there is no Differences in the attitudes of the faculty members at Umm Al-Qura University towards employing a "blackboard platform" in the educational process between faculty members due to the variable (specialization), and the result of the study (Shaghouf and El-Born, 2020), the results of which showed no differences in the trends of faculty members in Libya In emergencies and crises of variable (educational field).

- Degree variable:

Table (7) The results of the One Way ANOVA analysis of the differences between the averages of the study community’s responses towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19) depending on the (educational degree) variable.

The source of the contrast	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Average squareness	F value	Indication
Between groups	0.054	2	0.027	0.139	0.871
Within groups	18.442	94	0.196		No indication
Total	18.496	96			

*function at 0.05

It is evident from Table (7) that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance (0.05) between the averages of the study sample’s trends towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19) due to the degree variable, where the value of P was (0.139), It is not a function of (0.872).

This result is consistent with the result of the study (Al-Zahrani, 2020), whose results indicated that there are no differences in the attitudes of the faculty members at Umm Al-Qura University towards employing a "blackboard platform" in the educational process among faculty members attributable to a variable (academic degree), and the result of a study Shaghouf and ALWaldah, (2020), whose results showed that there are no differences in the attitudes of faculty members in Libya in emergency and crisis situations for the variable (academic degree). This result also differs with the result of the study (Al-Shehri, 2019), whose results showed that there are statistically significant differences between the attitudes of the faculty members in the Mathematics Department at King Khalid University towards the use of e-learning in teaching mathematics subjects to undergraduate students and students attributed to the variable (academic degree) in favor of Those with a degree (lecturers).

- Gender variable:

Table (8) the results of the T-Test for the differences between the averages of the study community's responses towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19) depending on the (gender) variable.

gender	the number	Average	standard deviation	T value	Degree of freedom	Indication
male	63	3.2841	0.44029	0.814	95	No indication
female	34	3.3063	0.43962			

It is evident from Table (8) that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance (0.05) between the averages of the study sample's trends towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19) due to the gender variable, where the value of T was (0.814), which is Not a function at (0.418).

This result is consistent with the result of the study (Al-Dhali, 2017), whose results indicated that there are no statistically significant differences between students' and faculty members 'attitudes towards e-learning at Najran University due to the variable (gender), and the study (Al-Shehri, 2019), whose results showed no differences Statistical significance between the averages of the faculty members 'trends in the Department of Mathematics at King Khalid University towards the use of electronic education in teaching mathematics subjects to undergraduate students due to the variable (gender), and the result of the study (Al-Zahrani, 2020), whose results indicated that there are no differences in the attitudes of members The faculty at Umm Al-Qura University is about employing a "blackboard platform" in the educational process among faculty members due to the variable (gender), and the result of a study (Shaghouf and El-born, 2020), whose results showed no differences in the trends of faculty members in Libya in emergency and crisis situations Variable (gender). This result also differs with the result of the study (Rabei, 2017), whose results indicated that there are statistically significant differences in the attitudes of university education professors at the University of Batna towards e-learning due to the (gender) variable in favor of (male) professors.

The previous results related to the second question indicate that the attitudes of the study community agree towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19) in various (academic departments, degrees, and gender) and that this trend does not differ according to (academic department, degree, or gender). The reason for this is that the faculty members in the College of Education at Taibah University were forced, like the rest of the universities of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, with its various departments, to go through the experiment. The study population members are close according to the different variables of the study.

Summary of results

It is evident from the results of the study that the attitudes of faculty members in the College of Education at Taibah University towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19) came with a medium degree, with a mean (3.310), and a standard deviation (0.438). There are no statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) between the averages of the study sample's trends towards distance education in light of the Corona pandemic (Covid-19) due to the study variables (academic department, degree, gender).

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, the researcher recommends the following:

- Adopting distance education as an effective strategic alternative to continue the educational process in the event of emergency or natural accidents.
- Benefiting from the best practices of Saudi universities in the field of distance education.
- Strengthening the strengths of the distance learning system followed at the university and developing weaknesses in it.
- Integration of traditional and distance education in the future.
- Providing various professional development programs and preparing guidelines related to the field of distance education, and updating them whenever needed.
- Providing the necessary material and moral support to work teams and faculty members in order to achieve achievements in the distance education system.
- Future studies

- Study the organizational culture that supports the application of distance education.
- Study the factors that attract students and teachers to study in the distance education system.
- Study assessing the skills and practices of faculty members related to the distance education system followed at the university.
- Studying the obstacles that faculty members faced when teaching in the remote education method from their point of view and ways to overcome them.
- Study the difficulties students faced when studying in a distance education method from their point of view and ways to overcome them.

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